

The International Academy for Systems and Cybernetic Sciences IASCYS

<http://iascys.org>

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What is the IASCYS ?

The IASCYS (The International Academy for Systems and Cybernetic Sciences) was initially established by IFSR (The International Federation for Systems Research) but is now open to all *“organizations covering or applying systems theories and cybernetics around the world“* (article added to the IFSR’s decision on establishment of IASCYS in 2010 and passed in 2012 http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Federation_for_Systems_Research). The IFSR current President is Garry Metcalf. The IFSR (<http://ifsr.org>) publishes 2 times a year a report on its activities in its on line newsletter, whose editor is the IFSR Secretary General, currently Gerhard Chroust. After a 2 years round of thinking and discussion (first IFSR board of trustees session, 26 **March 2008**), the Academy was founded by the IFSR in **April 2010**, the 7th, in Vienna (Austria). The founding members were: Matjaz Mulej (Slovenia) as President, Jifa Gu (PR China) and Ranulph Glanville (UK) as Vice-Presidents, Pierre Bricage (France) as Secretary General, Guangya Chen, Shouyang Wang and Jiuping Xu (PR China), Charles François and Enrique Herrscher (Argentina), Kyoichi Jim Kijima and Yoshiteru Nakamori (Japan), Andrej Wierzbicki (Poland) and Robert Vallée (France) President of WOSC (<http://wosc.co>).

The IFSR is a federation of national (like the American Society for Cybernetics ASC) and international societies. A half of the Societies are from European countries (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Nederland, Slovenia, Spain, for example). But, because of the presence of Argentina, Latino-Americana, Mexicana and Spain Societies, the second language is Spanish. But the IFSR is also a federation of international societies

(International Institute Galileo Galilei, International Institute of Informatics and Systemics, International Council on Systems Engineering, International Society for the Systems Sciences ISSS, World Complexity Science Academy WCSA and others). Indeed the IFSR is a federation of associations and federations. The societies that are the largest in membership are those from Asia (the Chinese, Japanese and Korean Societies). The largest one is the Chinese one. Indeed the first language of IFSR could be Chinese... The Chinese society has more members that the sum of all the others. So the IASCYS first General Assembly took place in **October 2010** in the Popular Republic of China, at Chengdu (Sichuan), with a week long international meeting [1].

The IASCYS what for ?

The Academy has two major missions: - Academic research of course, but also - promotion of education in systems science and cybernetics, not only higher education but at all education levels, and to create an auditing process through coordination of the actions of IFSR member associations for a worldwide accepted framework curriculum.

In order to achieve parts of the second goal, the Academy organises, since 4 years, and each 2 years, conjointly with the Bertalanffy Center for the Study of Systems Science (<http://www.bcsss.org>), which a member society of the IFSR, during the European Meeting on Cybernetics and Systems Research (EMCSR, <http://emcsr.net>) in Vienna (Austria) **the Ph.D. day competition** (<http://emcsr.net/calls-2014/calls-for-papers-2014/phd-colloquium-award>) (Figure 1). The first *Ludwig von Bertalanffy young scientist Award* (from BCSSS) was given in 2012, to Jessica Foley (from Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland) [2]. Katri-Liisa Pulkkinen (from

School of Engineering, Aalto University, Finland) won the second one in 2014 [3]. Each year, coming from all around the world, a different team of at least 16 benevolent experts in various fields of systems science and

cybernetics (from the Academy, from Academic or Engineering fields, from public and private structures) was evaluating the works of only 6 selected competitors from a larger group of applicants (Figure 1).

The European Meetings on Cybernetics and Systems Research traditionally focus on the foundations of system thinking across a variety of disciplinary domains and on its possible and intended impact on society and the amelioration of the human condition.

The EMCSR-PhD Colloquium is designed to promote inter- and trans-disciplinary research on various fields amenable to the system sciences as a means of disseminating ideas and concepts to other areas of system thinking and action and/or to support initiatives in system sciences education. The Colloquium invites all original and unpublished contributions to the field for consideration in competition for the prestigious Ludwig von Bertalanffy Young Scientist Award. After a round of selection, each admitted applicant attends all sessions associated with the EMCSR PhD-Day, not only as a speaker but also as a discussant to the contributions of all the other participants.

The Ludwig von Bertalanffy Young Scientist Award focuses on the inter- and trans-disciplinary capabilities of contestants as well as on their ability to incorporate the principle of “unity through diversity” in the content and application of their work. The award recipient is chosen on the basis of their ability to address a broader community of scholars and scientists with research that can also be **understood by interested non-specialists of the field.** The recipient of the award is recognized for **the best integrative trans-disciplinary work presented at the EMCSR PhD Colloquium.**

Figure 1. EMCSR 2014 PhD day world maps of competitors and judges.

For achieving parts of the first mission, the Academy organises workshops in international research meetings and sponsoring selected ones. This 2014 year the IASCYS is a sponsor of 8 meetings: - the two ASC (<http://www.asc-cybernetics.org>) and ISSS (<http://iss.org/world>) joint meetings (in Washington, USA), - the biennial EMCSR (<http://emcsr.net> in Vienna, Austria), - the IRDO (Institute for the Development of Social Responsibility) annual meeting

(<http://www.irdo.si> in Maribor, Slovenia), - the UES-EUS triennial meeting (<http://ues-wosc.com> in Valencia, Spain), -the biennial WCCS meeting (<http://www.wccs14.org> in Agadir Morocco), - the WCSA (<http://www.wcsaglobal.org> in Budapest, Hungary), - the Wiener World Celebration Conference of the IEEE (<http://21stcenturywiener.org> in Boston, USA) which is the world largest professional not-for-profit association for the advancement of

technology (<https://www.ieee.org/>).

During the 2014 sponsored EMCSR the Academy had a workshop on **Social and Environmental Responsibility**. Under the leadership of Matjaz Mulej and with the help of Bob Dyck, for the 10 years anniversary of IRDO, a 3 books volume series on Social Responsibility, as an open-to-all research project of IRDO and IASCYS for 4 years, was published by Bentham Science (USA) [4].

The Academy as a system: the function and functioning of the Academy.

Until today 35 Academicians have been appointed [5], an half in Europa, a quarter in America, a quarter in Asia and Oceania (Figure 2). The academy has no money and there is no fees to pay to be an Academician but a competitive entrance procedure. No registration fees, no membership dues, no contribution to be appointed, no subscription, all Academicians are elected through a competitive co-optation. Coming from the Academic and engineering worlds, the 35 Academicians are representing a wide variety of applied and fundamental domains (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Where and what are the Academicians: world map and domains chart (15 October 2014).

The Procedure for the Appointment of IASCYS Academicians (statutes -28 October 2010-) is the following. A potential candidate for the IASCYS must be a member of an IFSR or similar member Association [6]. The application must be submitted by this member association together with the candidate's credentials and all the required rooting documents, a detailed summary and evaluation score, according to the criteria for membership. No individual candidacy are allowed but only a Society supported one, because the IFSR is a federation of federations [7]. New criteria for IASCYS applicants have been voted by the 2010 first General Assembly, trusting out member societies, but allowing no upper limit on the points and a increase of the recruitment threshold. The 2 last Chinese appointed Academicians quoted more than 200 points in their application scoring [7].

The current Executive Committee of the Academy, elected unanimously with more than 2/3 of effective votings and for 4 years, during the second General Assembly in April 2014, in Vienna (Austria), is the following: Robert TRAPPL (Austria) as President, Jifa Gu (PR China), Matjaz Mulej (Slovenia) and Ranulph Glanville (UK) as Vice-Presidents, Pierre Bricage (France) as Secretary General.

References

[1] Gu J. & J. Xiu editors (25-27 October 2010) Proceedings of 2010 General Assembly of IASCYS, IFSR-IASCYS-Sichuan University at Chengdu (PR China), 71 p.

[2] Foley Jessica (13 April 2012) *The Important Case of Poetry, Telecommunications Engineering and von Bertalanffy's General System Theory*.

[3] Katri-Liisa Pulkkinen (22 April 2014) *A bottom-up way of building a system and changing perceptions - urban pioneers as a*

model for transformation for sustainability.

[4] Robert G. Dyck & Matjaž Mulej Editors, *Social Responsibility Beyond Neoliberalism and Charity*. Vol. 1: *Social Responsibility - A Non-technological Innovation Process*. Vol. 2: *Social Responsibility - Sustainability, Education and Management*. Vol. 3: *Social Responsibility - Methods, Dilemmas and Hopes*., Bentham Science Publishers, Oak Park, USA, August 2014, online eBooks.

[5] Mary Catherine **BATESON**, Ockert **BOSCH**, Pierre **BRICAGE**, Pille **BUNNEL**, Antonio **CASELLES MONCHO**, Guangya **CHEN**, Hanfu **CHEN**, Jian **CHEN**, Gerhard **CHROUST**, Charles **FRANCOIS**, Ranulph **GLANVILLE**, Jifa **GU**, Enrique **HERRSCHER**, Wolfgang **HOFKIRCHNER**, Michael **JACKSON**, Louis H. **KAUFFMAN**, Kyoichi J. **KIJIMA**, Ervin **LASZLO**, Humberto **MATURANA**, Edgar **MORIN**, Matjaz **MULEJ**, Yoshiteru **NAKAMORI**, Francisco **PARRA-LUNA**, Laurence D. **RICHARDS**, Bernard **SCOTT**, George **SOROS**, Robert **TRAPPL**, Stuart **UMPLEBY**, Robert **VALLÉE**, Ernst **von GLASERSFELD**, Shouyang **WANG**, Andrzej P. **WIERZBICKI**, Jennifer **WILBY**, Jiuping **XU**, Rainer E. **ZIMMERMANN**

Academicians past home-pages are at <http://www.armsada.eu/pb/academiciansAccueil.html>

[6] There are several organizations that have their roots in systems science and cybernetics. They might have candidates for IASCYS too.

[7] At <http://www.iascys.org> the first application sheet, ([Academicians' first Appointment](#)) at the foundation of the Academy, and the today new application sheet ([Academicians' new Criteria of election](#)) to become an Academician, and [Why to become an Academician?](#)